

TEACHERS AND STUDENTS' VIEWS ON VIOLENCE IN WESTERN KENYAN SCHOOLS

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Abstract: *Violence in secondary schools remains a critical concern, manifesting in various forms such as rioting, sexual violence, bullying, and physical altercations. This study investigates the perceptions of teachers and students regarding the psychological factors contributing to violent behavior in public secondary schools in the Western Province of Kenya. Grounded in Albert Bandura's social learning theory, the research employs a descriptive survey design. The study's sample comprised 638 principals, 6,354 teachers, and 65,969 form two students across 213 secondary schools, using stratified random sampling for students and purposive sampling for teachers. Data collection involved questionnaires and in-depth interviews, pilot-tested for reliability and validity. Qualitative data were analyzed through thematic coding, while quantitative data underwent descriptive statistical analysis, including frequency counts, means, and percentages, as well as inferential statistics like t-tests and Mann-Whitney U tests. Findings highlighted prevalent forms of violence—sexual violence, rioting, bullying, and fighting—and identified perceived psychological contributors such as anxiety, ethnic tensions, mental health issues, and fear of punishment. Students' perceptions of violence causes were consistent regardless of gender or school type. Recommendations include enhancing guidance and counseling services, establishing referral systems for students with psychological disorders, eliminating corporal punishment, creating effective communication channels, and re-evaluating ranking practices by educational authorities.*

Keywords: *School Violence, Psychological Factors, Secondary Education, Social Learning Theory Kenya*

INTRODUCTION

For centuries, violence has been a commonplace feature of school life with its causes embedded in the social, cultural, historical and economic contexts of its time. The **Abbreviations:** **AIDS**, Acquired immune deficiency syndrome; **ANOVA**, analysis of variance; **EFA**, education for all; **P.D.E**, provincial director of education; **U.S.A**, United States of America.

focus of violence can be individuals, objects or the school itself and the nature of the damage can be psychological, physical or material. Since the middle of the 20th century, violence against children has

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increasingly been viewed as a violation of their fundamental human rights, and in particular, their right to physical safety and psychological security and well-being (Leach, 2003). More recently, there has been a growing concern in understanding the roots of violence and the effects on all members of the school community and on the school culture and ethos itself, and to find constructive ways to reduce it when it occurs, and if possible, to prevent it. Three main problems that have been linked with school violence include interpersonal conflicts, low-level disruption and lack of discipline.

When such problems as these affect teaching and learning, there is a feeling of unrest throughout the school population. For instance, Ohsako (2007) claimed that the 1994 national survey in suburban, urban and rural schools in the United States of America found that two major factors were held responsible for school violence, that is, disintegration of the family and increased depiction of violence in the media and popular music. Other factors included alcohol and drug abuse and easy access to weapons, such as guns. Poverty and inequitable educational opportunities also predisposed school youths to violence.

Psychological factors are associated with the individual's thinking or mind and hence contribute to violent behavior among people. For instance, in Finland, Langerspetz et al. (1982) studied group aggression among 434 (12 – 16 years old) children in three schools. They found out that victims of violence, who had low esteem, were subjectively maladjusted and as such, experienced their peer relations negatively. The violent ones, on the other hand, were found to be physically strong and thus, frequently experienced handicaps than the well adjusted children. Additionally, the researchers observed that the bullies or aggressors held positive attitudes towards aggression and thus, experienced their peer relations negatively and held negative attitudes towards teachers. In 1982, Coie, Dodge and Coppabella studied 300 children aged between eight and fourteen years. Those children who were seen as "least like" were involved in disruptive activities such as fighting and acting snobbishly. They were also judged as being uncooperative, unsupportive and unattractive.

In a study on the relationship between age and bullying behavior, Olweus (1993) compared data from primary and secondary schools. He found the incidents of bullying to be twice as high in primary as in secondary schools. Bullies were found to be active in the last years of both primary and secondary schools, and several studies confirm a peak at 13 years. This hypothesis is supported by the findings that the bullies were least active on entering secondary school (that is, when they are the youngest students). Bullies of any age were found to be older than their victims. Over the school years, bullying among girls was perceived to decrease, whereas it increased among boys, although a general decrease was found in the physical bullying among the older pupils. The present study only focused on students in secondary schools unlike the previous investigation by Olweus, which involved respondents from primary and secondary schools.

In addition, Nansel et al. (2001) examined the frequency of various types of bullying as well as psychosocial adjustment of students who bully or who are bullied. Verbal bullying was most prominent

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for both males and females, with students being recipients of negative comments about their appearance in addition to being recipients of sexual comments and being targets of rumors. Interestingly, negative comments about race or religion were rarely reported. More males than females reported being victims of physical bullying, indicating that they had been hit, slapped and pushed. With regard to psychosocial adjustment, they found positive correlations between bullying behavior and fighting, alcohol use, smoking and ability to make friends. Poor academic achievement and poorer perceived school climate were also associated with being a bully. For middle school males, loneliness was also positively correlated with being a bully. However, negative correlations were found between victims in both alcohol usage and the ability to make friends, whereas being a victim was positively correlated with fighting. Loper et al. (2001) studied the relationship between characteristics of a violent event, as self-reported by 82 incarcerated juvenile offenders, and personality features measured by the 'million adolescent clinical inventory' (MACI). The study predicted that specific personality features that have previously been associated with psychopathy would be associated with the instrumentality, emotional reactivity and guilt reported for the incident. Results confirmed that a self-reported pattern of elevated instrumental motivation and reduced guilt was associated with higher scores on the MACI forceful, unruly, substance abuse proneness, impulsive propensity and family discord scales, as well as a recently developed psychopathy content scale. Self-reported elevated instrumental motivation and reduced empathy or guilt was also associated with lower scores on the submissive, conforming, anxious feelings and sexual discomfort scales. However, no significant relationships were observed between emotional reactivity and personality scales.

In addition, Stafford and Cornell (2003) found that psychopathy scores predicted aggressive behavior among 72 adolescent psychiatric inpatients. Psychopathy was assessed within three days of hospital admission by clinical raters trained in the use of Hare's psychopathy checklist, and the aggressive behavior was recorded by clinical staff that were unaware of psychopathy ratings. Adolescents that were rated higher in psychopathy exhibited higher frequencies of aggressive behavior, including physical aggression against peers and staff, than those that were rated lower in psychopathy. Psychopathy scores discriminated high and low aggressive youths with 71% accuracy, while 'receiver operating characteristic' analysis yielded an effective size. Learning institutions in Kenya for instance, have gradually gained notoriety as venues of sexual assault. Since the infamous St. Kizito incident, where 70 girls were raped while 19 others lost their lives when their male peers descended on them during what was supposed to be a school strike, several other group sexual violations have occurred

(ibid). Violent behavior is one of the practices that have scared teachers, parents and students, in which some students have died or suffered permanent deformities. Ruto (2009) asserted that violence has been going on since 1970 especially in boys' schools. In secondary schools, sexual violence has been identified as one of the most teething social problem young females are facing. Teachers have been reported to offer good or passing grades to girls in exchange for sex, and it is not uncommon for older

students to prey on girls as they walk to school or while they sleep in dormitories. Also, "sugar daddies" target girls in the vicinity of schools, luring them into sexual relations with gifts and money. Hence, many girls feel that their survival depends on such arrangements.

The causes of sexual violence vary greatly due to teachers' behaviour and traditional gender stereotypes. By not responding seriously to complaints of sexual abuse, teachers and school authorities convey the message that it could be tolerated. In addition, a lack of public prosecutions in many countries means that perpetrators are not held to account for their crimes. Girls in societies where women have a lower status are more likely to suffer sexual violence at school. In support of the aforementioned findings, Leach (2003) asserted that sexual abuse and violence are inextricably linked to other forms of physical violence in school, and in particular, to widespread bullying by learners and corporal punishment by educators on verbal abuse.

In addition, researchers have shown that violence among students can take place in many different locations within and outside the school. For instance, Olweus (1993) observed that bullying in secondary schools was one of the dark hidden areas of social interaction, along with child physical and sexual abuse and adolescent violence. Bullies and victims are both at risk for negative future outcomes. Kaiser and Rasminsky (2003) reported that as bullies go through adolescence they are more at risk for severe problems such as delinquency, alcohol and drug abuse and dropping out of school. In addition, both bullies and victims were found to be more depressed than students who were not involved in bullying (Seals and Young, 2003). Depression associated with bullying and victimization can lead to academic problems, self-defeating behaviors and interpersonal problems. Finally, victims are particularly at risk if there is no emotional support provided or if the bullying behavior is severe and prolonged. These victims are more likely to suffer from academic problems, absenteeism, loneliness and loss of friends (ibid).

In Kenya, Kigotho (1999) claimed that the well known form of bullying in Kenya had been the subtle type. This had been going on since 1970, especially in boys' schools. In such schools, victims of bullying were subjected to mental torture by being forced to answer several questions, give out money, shape their mouths funnily by moving jaws apart and sideways according to the instructions from a bully's palms and to sing obscene songs. In girls' schools on the other hand, less violence had been reported and bullying had mainly been in the form of name-calling, taunting and threats. As a result of that, it is still difficult to prove that some one was bullied (involving rape), except where some physical force was visibly used. Indeed, violence has resulted in many dire consequences on students' social and academic endeavor. For instance, Ohsako (2007) discovered during his work on truancy that approximately 19% of truants had started to miss school because of bullying and had continued to miss school for this same reason. The act of being bullied tends to increase some students' isolation because their peers do not want to lose status by associating with their risks of being bullied (Kisia, 2010). Eventually, victims of this form of violence experience depression and low esteem (problems that can be carried into

adulthood). Mathiu (2008) noted that over the past decade, many secondary schools had suffered from strikes most of which placed head teachers in the spot light. For instance, in 1991, male students in a mixed high school invaded the girls ‘dormitory and raped more than 70 girls, of which 19 female students lost their lives at a tender age of 15. In another incident in 1999, a group of male students locked up 4 prefects in their cubicles at night and doused them in petrol killing them instantly. The worst calamity was in 2001 when 68 students were burnt to death and some injured after their dormitory was set on fire by two boys who petrol bombed the school. Consequently, several reasons were advanced by different stakeholders as the underlying root causes of riots in schools. They included: overloaded curriculum, autocratic school administration, drug and substance abuse, poor living conditions in schools, excessive use of corporal punishment, lack of an effective school guidance and counseling service, pressure for excellent academic performance, abdication of parental responsibility, incompetent board of governors, culture of impunity in the society and adolescence identity crisis and mass media campaigns. In 2008, over 254 secondary schools experienced the ongoing orgy of violence in Kenya per province as follows: Central (68), Rift valley (55), Eastern (53), Nyanza (27), Coast (24), Nairobi (19), Western (8) and North Eastern has none (Kuchio and Njagi, 2008). Therefore in order to reduce escalating anxiety among parents, teachers and students over the impact of violence, there was need to study teachers’ and students’ perceptions of psychological factors contributing to violent behavior in secondary schools. That laid the foundation for seeking solutions to the problem.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Western Province that has 21 districts. The social learning theory by Albert Bandura (1977) formed the basis of the study. Learning of any behavior such as violence by students is due to reinforcement, imitation and identification.

Table 1. Perceptions of forms of violent behaviour between male and female students.

Forms of violence	of Gender	Number respondents	of Mean rank	Ranks
Bullying	Male	656		
	Female	496	544.50	4
	Total	1152	618.82	1
Fighting	Male	656		
	Female	496	564.92	3
	Total	1152	591.82	2

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Rioting	Male	656	569.41	2
	Female	496	585.88	3
	Total	1152		
Sexual violence	Male	656	617.66	1
	Female	496	522.06	4
	Total	1152		

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design covering a population of 6,354 secondary school teachers, 638 principals and 65,969 form two secondary school students from 638 public secondary schools. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select public secondary schools and in addition, a formula recommended by Fisher et al. (1983) was used to calculate the number of selected form two students on the basis of their gender and type of secondary school, while purposive sampling technique was used to select teachers from the sampled public secondary schools for the study. Therefore, 364 teachers and 1,152 form two students from 213 public secondary schools participated in the study.

In the current study, both questionnaires and in-depth interview guides were used to collect data. A pilot study was carried out in four schools of girls and boys to establish reliability of the research instruments. To establish face validity, the research instruments were given to three experts from the Department of Educational Psychology to verify their validity. Qualitative data were transcribed, put into various categories and thereafter reported according to the emergent themes, whereas quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, mean and frequency counts were used, while inferential statistics such as Mann-Whitney U-test and t-test statistics were also used.

The Mann-Whitney U-test was used to establish the significant differences in male and female group means, while the t-test was used to establish the difference between teachers' and students' ranks on factors contributing to violent behavior. However, data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 11.0 version for windows.

RESULTS

The study addressed the following objectives: to establish forms of violent behavior experienced by secondary school students as perceived by teachers and students and to establish psychological factors contributing to violent behavior in secondary schools as perceived by teachers and students.

Forms of violent behavior experienced by secondary school students as perceived by teachers and students

In order to meet this first objective of the study, the respondents were provided with a listing of possible forms of violent behaviour and asked to rank each of the listed forms. The responses were summarized and presented in Table 1. According to Table 1, forms of violence were ranked as follows by male

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students: sexual violence first, rioting second and fighting third. Male students identified bullying as the least form of violent behaviour. On the other hand, scores given by female students indicated that bullying was first, fighting was second, rioting was third and sexual violence was fourth. To test for any significant difference between male and female students, the Mann-Whitney U test statistics was applied. The Mann-Whitney U test statistics and Wilcoxon W had values of 162510 and 378006 respectively, with an associated two tail significance level of 0.943. Since the significance value of 0.943 was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that male students did not differ significantly from female students in their perceptions of forms of violent behaviour.

Perceptions of forms of violence between students in rural secondary schools and students in urban secondary schools

The respondents were provided with a list of possible forms of violent behaviour and asked to rank each of the listed forms. The responses are summarized and presented in Figure 1. From Figure 1, ranks of scores assigned to the forms of violence by students in rural schools were as follows: sexual violence was first, rioting was second and fighting was third. Students in rural schools identified bullying as the least form of violent behaviour. On the other hand, scores given by students in urban schools indicated that bullying was first, fighting was second, rioting was third and sexual violence was fourth. To test the significant difference between two groups of respondents, the Mann-Whitney U test statistics was applied. The Mann-Whitney U test statistics had a value of 76963.5 and Wilcoxon W had a value of 157163.5 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.550. Since the significance value of 0.550 was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, it was concluded that students in rural schools did not differ significantly from students in urban schools in their perceptions of forms of violence. As it pertains to Table 2, male teachers ranked sexual violence to come first, bullying as second and rioting as third. As such, they identified fighting as the least form of violence. On the other hand, female teachers perceived rioting to come first, fighting as second, sexual violence as third and bullying and fighting as fourth. In order to test for any significant difference between two groups of respondents, the Mann-Whitney U test statistics was applied. The Mann-Whitney U test statistics had a value of 10442.5 and the Wilcoxon W had a value of 32808.5 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.000. Since the significance value of 0.000 was less than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that male teachers differed significantly from female teachers in their perceptions of forms of violent behaviour. The differences in the perceptions among teachers could be attributed to gender differences. These findings concur to some extent with those of Olweus (1993) who established that bullying in secondary schools is one of the dark hidden areas of social interaction, along with child physical and sexual abuse and adolescent violence.

According to Table 3, the teachers in rural secondary schools ranked sexual violence to come first, bullying as second and fighting as third. In addition, they identified rioting as the least form of violence. On the other hand, respondents in urban secondary schools perceived rioting first, fighting second, bullying third and sexual violence fourth. In order to the test for any significant difference between two

groups of respondents, the Mann-Whitney U test statistics was applied. The MannWhitney U test statistics had a value of 10852.5 and the Wilcoxon W had a value of 29188.5 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.000. Since the significance value of 0.000 was less than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that teachers in rural secondary schools differed significantly from teachers in urban secondary schools in their perceptions of forms of violent behaviour.

Figure 1. Perceptions of forms of violence between students in rural secondary schools and students in urban secondary schools.

Psychological factors contributing to violent behavior in secondary schools as perceived by teachers and students

In order to meet this third objective, the respondents were provided with a list of possible psychological factors contributing to violent behavior and were asked to indicate which of the listed psychological factors contributed to violent behavior in secondary schools. According to Table 4, 62.3 and 52.6% of

Table 2. Perceptions of forms of violence between male and female teachers.

Forms of violence	of Gender respondents	of Number respondents	of Mean rank	Ranks
Bullying	Male	211		
	Female	153	171.81	2
	Total	364	197.24	3
Fighting	Male	211		
	Female	153	156.14	4
	Total	364	217.47	2
Rioting	Male	211		
	Female	153	156.20	3
	Total	364	218.77	1
Sexual Violence	Male	211		
	Female	153	218.34	1
	Total	364	133.07	4

Table 3. Perceptions of forms of violence between teachers in rural secondary schools and teachers in urban secondary schools.

Forms of violence	Location of schools		Number of respondents	Mean rank	Ranks
Bullying	Rural schools	191			
	Urban schools	173	175.23	2	
	Total	364	190.53	3	
Fighting	Rural schools	191			
	Urban schools	153	157.97	3	
	Total	364	209.58	2	
Rioting	Rural schools	191			
	Urban schools	173	150.29	4	
	Total	364	218.07	1	

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	Rural schools	191		
Sexual violence	Urban schools	173	218.97	1
	Total	364	142.24	4

the male and female respondents, respectively, agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors contributing to violent behavior among students, while 27.9 and 36.5% of the male and female students, respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 46.5 and 40.7% of the male and female students, respectively. However, 36.3 and 44.3%

of the male and female students expressed disagreement with the statement. In addition, 30.5 and 30% of the male and female students, respectively expressed agreement with being talkative.

However, 53.5 and 53.8% of the male and female students respectively were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, 38 and 30.8% of the male and female students respectively expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 40.8 and 42.5% of the male and female students respectively were in disagreement. More so, 60.3 and 51% of the male and female students respectively, identified ethnic violence as a cause of violence. The same statement was not supported by 22.1 and 21.2% of the male and female students respectively.

In addition, 40.3 and 41.3% of the male and female students, respectively, agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students.

Table 4. Perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between male and female students in secondary schools.

Statement	Gender	Strongly agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
		Experiencing mental illness	Male	210	32	199	30.3	64	9.8	77	11.7	106	16.2
	Female	138	27.8	123	24.8	54	10.9	85	17.1	96	19.4	496	100
Being over confident	Male	108	16.5	197	30	113	17.2	152	23.2	86	13.1	656	100
	Female	77	15.5	125	25.2	74	15	134	27	86	17.3	496	100
Being a talkative	Male	67	10.2	132	20.3	106	16	194	29.6	157	23.9	656	100
	Female	58	11.7	93	18.3	78	16.2	140	28.2	127	25.6	496	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	Male	125	19.1	124	18.9	113	17.2	155	23.6	139	21.2	656	100
	Female	78	15.7	75	15.1	87	17.6	124	25	132	26.6	496	100
Ethnic violence	Male	197	30	199	30.3	115	17.6	72	11	73	11.1	656	100
	Female	152	30.6	132	26.4	102	20.8	59	11.9	51	10.3	496	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	Male	112	17.1	152	23.2	115	17.4	152	23.2	125	19.1	656	100
	Female	79	15.9	126	25.4	86	17.4	123	24.8	82	16.5	496	100

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Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers Depression	Male	287	43.8	206	31.4	66	10	53	8.1	44	6.7	656	100
	Female	194	39.1	155	31.3	53	10.6	53	10.7	41	8.3	496	100
Experiencing communication Problems	Male	119	18.1	158	24.1	155	23.7	122	18.6	102	15.5	656	100
	Female	108	21.8	85	17.1	86	17.3	121	24.4	96	19.4	496	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indiscipline	Male	127	19.4	128	19.5	109	16.6	156	23.8	136	20.7	656	100
	Female	119	24	107	21.6	72	14.4	97	19.6	101	20.4	496	100
Fear of losing friends	Male	133	20.3	167	25.5	88	13	136	20.8	132	20.2	656	100
	Female	112	22.6	114	23	64	12.8	97	19.6	109	22	496	100
Fear of being punished	Male	150	22.9	159	24.2	89	15.5	129	19.7	129	17.7	656	100
	Female	102	20.6	119	24	67	13.4	96	19.4	112	22.6	496	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	Male	155	23.6	127	19.4	108	16.1	133	20.6	133	20.3	656	100
	Female	120	24.2	121	24.1	85	17.5	87	17.5	83	16.7	496	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	Male	169	25.8	98	14.9	60	9.2	121	18.4	208	31.7	656	100
	Female	130	26.2	114	23	52	10.5	80	16.1	120	24.2	496	100

However, 40.7 and 41.3% of the male and female by 14.8 and 21.4% of the male and female students respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, experiencing communication statement. Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 32.2 and 38.9% of the male and female students respectively, as 34.1 and 43.8% of the male and female students respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. The male and female students who agreed to the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline by the male and female students respectively is a cause of violence, accounted for 38.9 and 45.6% of the male and female students respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 44.5 and 40% of the male and female students respectively. Fear of losing friends was supported by 45.8 and 45.6% of the male and female students

respectively. However, 34.1 and 33.5% of the male students and female students respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 47.1 and 44.6% of the male and female students respectively. However, 37.4 and 42% of the male and female students respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 43 and 48.3% of the male and female students respectively, while 36.6 and 34.2% of the male and female students respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Male and female students who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 40.7 and 49.2% respectively. However, 27.5 and 26.6% of the male and female students respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. In order to test if there was any significant difference of perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between male and female students, a t-test statistics was used.

The t-test statistics under the assumption of equal variances had a value of -0.331 and the degree of freedom had a value of 1150 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.741. Since the significance value of 0.741 is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that male students did not differ significantly from female students in their perceptions of home factors that contribute to violent behaviour. These findings concur to some extent with that of Olweus (1993) who found out that family communication problems and parental mental disorder were the major causes of behavioral problems. With reference to Table 5, 70.3 and 56.5% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 21.3 and 23.9% in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 66.5 and 40.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. However, 36.8 and 44.5% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools, expressed disagreement with the statement. In boys' schools and girls' schools, 28.8 and 27.2% of the respondents respectively, expressed agreement with being talkative. However, 58.3 and 58.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, 40.3 and 29.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 42.3 and 53.2% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement.

Ethnic violence was supported by 68.6 and 62.7% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, while the same statement was not supported by 14.8% and 18.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. In boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, 43.1 and 42.2% of the respondents agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 40.1 and 40.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively,

were in disagreement with the statement. Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 85.8 and 75.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. As such, the statement was not supported by 40.6 and 15% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 44.6 and 38.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, while 40.5 and 43.4% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline as a cause of violence accounted for 37.3 and 43.4% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 45.1 and 42.2% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. Fear of losing friends was supported by 49.8 and 44% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively. As such, 19.4% of the respondents in boys' schools and 44% of the respondents in girls' schools were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' schools and respondents in girls' schools who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 46.5 and 41.7% respectively. However, 44% of the respondents in boys' schools and 41.3% of the respondents in girls' schools were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 42.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and 46% of the respondents in girls' schools, while 43.6 and 36.2% of the respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' schools and girls' schools who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 34.8 and 46.1% respectively. However, 57.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and 33.2% of the respondents in girls' schools were in disagreement with the statement. To test for the significant difference of perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in boys' schools and girls' schools, a t-test statistics was employed. The t-test statistics under the assumption of equal variances had a value of -0.480 and the degree of freedom had a value of 0.598 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.631. Since the significance value of 0.631 was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, it was concluded that students in boys' schools did not differ significantly from students in girls' schools in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour. With reference to Table 6, 56.5 and 46.5% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively agreed experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 33.9 and 40.5% in girls' schools and coeducational schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 40.1% of the respondents in girls' schools and 44.9% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, 36.8 and 38% of the respondents in girls' schools and coeducational schools expressed disagreement with the statement. In girls' schools and co-educational schools, 27.2 and 35.8% of the respondents respectively expressed agreement with being talkative. However, 58.1% of the respondents in girls' and 43.8% of the respondents in co-educational

schools were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, 34.2 and 19.1% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 53.2 and 53.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and coeducational schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Ethnic violence was supported by 62.7% of the respondents in girls' schools and 44.4% of the respondents in co-educational schools, but the same statement was not supported by 18.6 and 45.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively. In girls' schools and co-educational schools, 42.2 and 36.7% of the respondents respectively agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 40.6% of the respondents in girls' schools and 45.2% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement.

Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 75.1% of the respondents in girls' schools and 57% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, the statement was not supported by 15 and 28.6% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 38.6 and 38.6% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively, while 43.4% of the respondents in girls' schools and 43.4% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline as a cause of violence accounted for 43.4% of the respondents in girls' schools and 43.8% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 42.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and 40.2% of the respondents in co-educational schools. Fear of losing friends was supported by 43.8% of the respondents in girls' schools and 43.1% of the respondents in coeducational schools. However, 40.2 and 42.5% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 41.7% of the respondents in girls' schools and 46.8% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, 45.2 and 43.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and co-educational schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 46% of the respondents in girls' schools and 47.9% of the respondents in co-educational schools, while 36.2 and 34.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and coeducational schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in girls' schools and coeducational schools who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 46.1 and 53.2% respectively. However, 43.2% of the respondents in girls' schools and 36.6% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement. In order to test if there was any significant difference in perceptions of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in girls' schools and

co-educational schools, a t-test statistics was used. The t-test statistics under the assumption of unequal variances had a value of -0.450, while the degree of freedom had a value of 761.495 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.653. Since the significance value of 0.653 was greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that students in girls' schools did not differ significantly from students in co-educational schools in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour. With reference to Table 7, 70.3% of the respondents in boys' schools and 46.5% of the respondents in co-educational schools agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 21.3 and 40.5% of the respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 66.5% of the respondents in boys' schools and 44.9% of the respondents in coeducational schools. However, 36.8 and 38% of the respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools, respectively, expressed disagreement with the statement. In boys' schools and girls' schools, 28.8 and 35.8% of the respondents respectively expressed agreement with being talkative, while 58.3% of the respondents in boys' schools and 43.8% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement.

In addition, 40.3 and 19.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools respectively expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 42.3% of the respondents in boys' schools and 53.2% of the respondents in coeducational schools were in disagreement with the statement. Ethnic violence was supported by 68.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and 44.4% of the respondents in co-educational schools. The same statement was not supported by 14.8 and 45.2% of the respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools respectively. In boys' schools and co-educational schools, 43.1 and 36.7% of the respondents respectively agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 40.1 and 45.2% of the respondents were in disagreement with the statement. Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 85.8% of the respondents in boys' schools and 57% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, the statement was not supported by 40.6 and 28.6% of the respondents in both boys' and co-educational schools respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 44.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and 38.6% of the respondents in coeducational schools, while 40.5 and 43.4% of the respondents in both boys' and co-educational schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' secondary schools and girls' secondary schools who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline as a cause of violence accounted for 37.3 and 43.8% of the respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 45.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and 40.2% of the respondents in co-educational schools. Fear of losing friends was supported by 49.8% of the respondents in boys' schools and 43.1% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, 19.4

and 42.5% of the respondents in both boys' and coeducational schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' schools and coeducational schools who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 46.5% of the respondents in boys' schools and 46.8% of the respondents in co-educational schools. However, 44 and 43.2% of the respondents in both boys' and co-educational schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 42.6 and 47.9% of the respondents in boys' and co-educational schools respectively, while 43.6% of the respondents in boys' schools and 34.2% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in boys' schools and co-educational schools who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 34.8 and 53.2% respectively. However, 57.1% of the respondents in boys' schools and 36.6% of the respondents in co-educational schools were in disagreement with the statement.

In order to test if there was any significant difference in perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in boys' schools and co-educational schools, a t-test statistics was employed. The t-test statistics under the assumption of equal variances had a value of -0.952 and the degree of freedom had a value of 760 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.341. Since the significance value of 0.341 was greater than $\alpha=0.05$, it was concluded that students in boys' schools did not differ significantly from students in co-educational schools in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour. With reference to Table 8, 56.5% of the respondents in rural schools and 46.5% of the respondents in urban schools agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 33.9 and 40.5% in both girls' and co-educational schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 40.1% of the respondents in rural schools and 44.9% of the respondents in urban schools. However, 36.8 and 38% of the respondents in rural and urban schools expressed disagreement with the statement. In rural and urban schools, 27.2 and 35.8% of the respondents respectively expressed agreement with being talkative. However, 58.1 and 43.8% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement.

In addition, 34.2% of the respondents in rural schools and 19.1% of the respondents in urban schools expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 53.2 and 53.2% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Ethnic violence was supported by 62.7% of the respondents in rural schools and 44.4% of the respondents in urban schools, whereas the same statement was not supported by 18.6 and 45.2% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively. In rural and urban schools, 42.2 and 36.7% of the respondents respectively agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 40.6 and 45.2% of the respondent in rural and urban schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement.

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Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 75.1% of the respondents in rural schools and 57% of the respondents in urban schools. However, the statement was not supported by 15 and 28.6% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 38.6% of the respondents in rural schools and 38.6% of the respondents in urban schools, while 43.4 and 43.4% of the respondents in rural and urban schools were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in both rural and urban schools who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline is a cause of violence, accounted for 43.4% and 43.8% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 42.2 and 40.2% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively. Fear of losing friends was supported by 43.8% of the respondents in rural schools and 43.1% of the respondents in urban schools. However, 40.2 and 42.5% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in rural and urban schools who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 41.7 and 46.8% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively. However, 45.2% of the respondents in rural schools and 43.2% of the respondents in urban schools were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 46% of the respondents in rural schools and 47.9% of the respondents in urban schools, while 36.2 and 34.2% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents in rural and urban schools who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 46.1 and 53.2% respectively. However, 43.2 and 36.6% of the respondents in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. In order to test if there was any significant difference in perceptions of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in rural and urban schools, a t-test statistics was used. The t-test statistics under the assumption of unequal variances had a value of -0.450 and the degree of freedom had a value of 761.495 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.653. Since the significance value of 0.653 was greater than $\alpha=0.05$, it implied that male students in rural schools did not differ significantly from students in urban schools in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour. According to Table 9, 78.2 and 75.8% of the male and female teachers respectively, agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 17.4 and 18.1% of the male and female teachers respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 28.9% of the male teachers and 34.7% of the female teachers. However, 17.1 and 23.6% of the male and female teachers, respectively, expressed disagreement with the statement. In addition, 15.2% of the male teachers and 19.6% of the female teachers expressed agreement with being talkative. However, 25.6 and 72.5% of the male and female teachers respectively were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, 74.7% of the male teachers and 64.5% of the female teachers expressed

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agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 22.6 and 30.3% of the male and female teachers respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Ethnic violence was supported by 88.6% of the male teachers and 88.3% of the female teachers, while the same statement was not supported by 16.1 and 12.4% of the male and female teachers respectively.

In addition, 67.5% of the male teachers and 71.2% of the female teachers agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 32 and 8.6% of the male and female teachers, respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 82.7% of the male teachers and 76.8% of the female teachers, but the statement was not supported by 10.2 and 29.2% of the male and female teachers respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 80.6% of the male teachers and 75.2% of the female teachers, while 15.9 and 18.9% of the male and female teachers were in disagreement with the statement. The male and female teachers who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline is a cause of violence, accounted for 69.6 and 72.6% of the male and female teachers respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 21.8% of the male teachers and 18.6% of the female teachers. Fear of losing friends was supported by 26.6% of the male teachers and 30.7% of the female teachers. However, 21.8 and 65.4% of the male and female teachers respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 47.4 and 48.5% of the male and female teachers respectively. However, 38.8% of the male teachers and 45.3% of the female teachers were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 22.1% of the male teachers and 63.4% of the female teachers, while 12.3 and 28.8% of the male and female teachers respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Male and female teachers who were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 20.8 and 60.2% respectively. However, 74.9 and 34% of the male and female teachers respectively were in disagreement with the statement.

In order to test if there was any significant difference in perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between male and female teachers, a t-test statistics was used. The t-test statistics under the assumption of equal variances had a value of 0.134 and the degree of freedom had a value of 213.294 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.000. Since the significance value of 0.000 was less than $\alpha=0.05$, it implied that male teachers differed significantly from female teachers in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour. The situation could be attributed to their differences in gender. Nansel et al. (2001) observed that there were positive correlations between bullying behavior and fighting, alcohol use, smoking, loneliness and ability to make friends. This concurs with the findings of the current study. Similarly, Unnever and Cornell

(2003) found out that low selfcontrol and attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) status were potential risk factors for bullying and victimization.

According to Table 10, 76.2% of the teachers in rural secondary schools and 70.2% of the teachers in urban secondary schools agreed that experiencing mental illness was one of the psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among students, while 14.6 and 24.3% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively were in disagreement with the statement. Being overconfident was supported by 70.2% of the teachers in rural schools and 75.4% of the teachers in urban schools. However, 23.6 and 16.5% of the teachers in rural and urban schools, respectively, expressed disagreement with the statement. In addition, 14.1% of the teachers in rural schools and 10.7% of the teachers in urban schools expressed agreement with being talkative. However, 26.7 and 73.4% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. In addition, 74.2% of the teachers in rural schools and 57.2% of the teachers in urban schools expressed agreement with the statement that fear and uncertainty of unemployment in future contributes to violence in schools. However, 17.8 and 28.9% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Ethnic violence was supported by 89.5% of the teachers in rural schools and 70.8% of the teachers in urban schools, while the same statement was not supported by 7.8 and 11.8% of the teachers in rural and urban schools, respectively.

Table 5. Perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in boys’ secondary schools (B/Sch.) and students in girls’ secondary schools (G/Sch.).

Statement	School type	Strongly agree				Agree				Undecided				Disagree				Strongly disagree				Total	
		F		%		F		%		F		%		F		%		F		%		F	%
Experiencing mental illness	B/Sch.	151	37.8	130	32.5	34	8.4	38	9.5	47	11.8	400	100										
	G/Sch.	120	30.8	100	25.7	37	9.6	63	16.2	69	17.7	389	100										
Being over confident	B/Sch.	59	14.8	129	32.2	65	16.2	91	22.8	56	14.0	400	100										
	G/Sch.	63	16.2	93	23.9	60	15.4	107	27.5	66	17.0	389	100										
Being a talkative	B/Sch.	40	10.0	75	18.8	52	12.9	128	32.0	105	26.3	400	100										
	G/Sch.	44	11.3	62	15.9	57	14.7	116	29.8	110	28.3	389	100										
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	B/Sch.	74	18.5	91	22.8	66	16.4	89	22.3	80	20.0	400	100										
	G/Sch.	64	16.5	49	12.6	69	17.7	104	26.7	103	26.5	389	100										
Ethnic violence	B/Sch.	139	34.8	135	33.8	67	16.4	33	8.3	26	6.5	400	100										

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	G/Sch.	132	33.9	112	28.8	73	18.7	36	9.3	36	9.3	389	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	B/Sch.	77	19.3	95	23.8	68	16.8	93	23.3	67	16.8	400	100
	G/Sch.	64	16.5	100	25.7	67	17.2	99	25.4	59	15.2	389	100
Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers	B/Sch.	210	52.5	133	33.3	28	6.9	17	4.3	12	3.0	400	100
	G/Sch.	170	43.7	122	31.4	39	9.9	63	9.3	22	5.7	389	100
Depression	B/Sch.	75	18.8	103	25.8	60	14.9	96	24.0	66	16.5	400	100
	G/Sch.	84	21.6	66	17.0	70	18.0	86	22.1	83	21.3	389	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indiscipline	B/Sch.	78	19.5	75	18.8	67	16.4	97	24.3	83	20.8	400	100
	G/Sch.	99	25.4	70	18.0	56	14.4	80	20.6	84	21.6	389	100
Fear of losing friends	B/Sch.	90	22.5	109	27.3	52	12.8	74	18.5	75	18.9	400	100
	G/Sch.	87	22.4	84	21.6	47	12.0	75	19.3	96	24.7	389	100
Fear of being punished	B/Sch.	94	23.5	92	23.0	49	12.2	80	20.0	85	21.3	400	100
	G/Sch.	78	20.1	84	21.6	51	13.1	77	19.8	99	25.4	389	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	B/Sch.	95	23.8	75	18.8	56	13.8	77	19.3	97	24.3	400	100
	G/Sch.	96	24.7	83	21.3	69	17.8	72	18.5	69	17.7	389	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	B/Sch.	90	22.5	49	12.3	33	8.1	83	20.8	145	36.3	400	100
	G/Sch.	94	24.2	85	21.9	42	10.7	66	17.0	102	26.2	389	100

Table 6. Perceptions of psychological factors contributing to violent behaviour between students in girls' secondary schools (G/Sch.) and students in co-educational secondary school (Co-ed. Sch.).

Statement	School type	Strongly agree				Agree				Undecided				Disagree				Strongly disagree				Total	
		F		%		F		%		F		%		F		%		F		%		F	%
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Experiencing mental	G/Sch.	120	30.8	100	25.7	37	9.6	63	16.2	69	17.7	389	100										

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illness	Co-ed. Sch.	77	21.2	92	25.3	47	13.0	61	16.8	86	23.7	363	100
Being over confident	G/Sch.	63	16.2	93	23.9	60	15.4	107	27.5	66	17.0	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	63	17.4	100	27.5	62	17.1	88	24.2	50	13.8	363	100
Being a talkative	G/Sch.	44	11.3	62	15.9	57	15.0	116	29.8	110	28.3	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	41	11.3	89	24.5	74	20.4	90	24.8	69	19.0	363	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	G/Sch.	64	16.5	49	12.6	69	17.7	104	26.7	103	26.5	389	100
	Co-ed.	65	17.9	59	16.3	65	17.9	86	23.7	88	24.2	363	100
	Sch.												
Ethnic violence	G/Sch.	132	33.9	112	28.8	73	18.7	36	9.3	36	9.3	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	78	21.5	83	22.9	38	10.4	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	G/Sch.	64	16.5	100	25.7	67	17.2	99	25.4	59	15.2	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	50	13.8	83	22.9	66	18.1	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, temper Depression	G/Sch.	170	43.7	122	31.4	39	9.9	36	9.3	22	5.7	389	100
	Co-ed.	101	27.8	106	29.2	52	14.4	53	14.6	51	14.0	363	100
	Sch.												
Experiencing communication problems	G/Sch.	84	21.6	66	17.0	70	18.0	86	22.1	83	21.3	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	68	18.7	74	20.4	58	16.0	94	25.9	69	19.0	363	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indisciplin	G/Sch.	99	25.4	70	18.0	56	14.4	80	20.6	84	21.6	389	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	69	19.0	90	24.8	58	16.0	76	20.9	70	19.3	363	100

Table 7. Perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between students in boys' secondary schools (B/Sch.) and students in co-educational secondary schools (Co-ed.Sch.).

Statement	School type	Strongly agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Fear of being punished	B/Sch.	151	37.8	130	32.5	34	8.4	38	9.5	47	11.8	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	77	21.2	92	25.3	47	13.0	61	16.8	86	23.7	363	100
Experiencing mental illness	B/Sch.	59	14.8	129	32.3	65	16.5	91	23.2	56	14.3	389	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	63	17.4	100	27.5	62	17.1	88	24.2	50	13.8	363	100
Being overconfident	B/Sch.	84	23.1	90	24.8	65	17.9	71	19.6	53	14.6	363	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	40	10.0	75	18.8	52	12.9	128	32.0	105	26.3	400	100
parental expectations	B/Sch.	41	10.3	89	22.9	74	19.0	96	24.8	60	15.2	363	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	115	31.7	78	21.5	37	10.2	52	14.3	81	22.3	363	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	B/Sch.	74	18.5	91	22.8	66	16.4	89	22.3	80	20.0	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	65	17.9	59	16.3	65	17.9	86	23.7	88	24.2	363	100
Ethnic violence	B/Sch.	139	34.8	135	33.8	67	17.1	33	8.3	26	6.5	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	78	21.5	83	22.9	38	10.4	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	B/Sch.	77	19.3	95	23.8	68	16.8	93	23.3	67	16.8	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	50	13.8	83	22.9	66	18.1	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers	B/Sch.	210	52.5	133	33.3	28	6.9	17	4.3	12	3.0	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	101	27.8	106	29.2	52	14.4	53	14.6	51	14.0	363	100
Experiencing communication problems	B/Sch.	75	18.8	103	25.8	60	14.9	96	24.0	66	16.5	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	68	18.7	74	20.4	58	16.0	94	25.9	69	19.0	363	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indiscipline	B/Sch.	78	19.5	75	18.8	67	16.6	97	24.3	83	20.8	400	100
	Co-ed.Sch.	69	19.0	90	24.8	58	16.0	76	20.9	70	19.3	363	100
Fear of losing friends	B/Sch.	90	22.5	109	27.3	52	12.9	74	18.5	75	18.8	400	100

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	Co-ed. Sch.	68	18.8	88	24.3	53	14.4	84	23.2	70	19.3	363	100
Fear of being punished	B/Sch.	94	23.5	92	23.0	49	12.2	80	20.0	85	21.3	400	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	80	22.0	90	24.8	69	19.0	71	19.6	53	14.6	363	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	B/Sch.	95	23.8	75	18.8	56	13.8	77	19.3	97	24.3	400	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	84	23.1	90	24.8	65	17.9	71	19.6	53	14.6	363	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	B/Sch.	90	22.5	49	12.3	33	8.1	83	20.8	145	36.3	400	100
	Co-ed. Sch.	115	31.7	78	21.5	37	10.2	52	14.3	81	22.3	363	100

Table 8. Perceptions of psychological factors contributing to violent behaviour between students in rural secondary schools (Rural Sch.) and students in urban secondary schools (Urban Sch.).

Statement	Location of schools	Strongly agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Experiencing mental illness	Rural Sch.	120	30.8	100	25.7	37	9.6	63	16.2	69	7.7	389	100
	Urban Sch.	77	21.2	92	25.3	47	13.0	61	16.8	86	23.7	363	100
Being over confident	Rural Sch.	63	16.2	93	23.9	60	15.4	107	27.5	66	17.0	389	100
	Urban Sch.	63	17.4	100	27.5	62	17.1	88	24.2	50	13.8	363	100
Being a talkative	Rural Sch.	44	11.3	62	15.9	57	15.0	116	29.8	110	28.3	389	100
	Urban Sch.	41	11.3	89	24.5	74	20.4	90	24.8	69	19.0	363	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	Rural Sch.	64	16.5	49	12.6	69	17.7	104	26.7	103	26.5	389	100
	Urban Sch.	65	17.9	59	16.3	65	17.9	86	23.7	88	24.2	363	100
Ethnic violence	Rural Sch.	132	33.9	112	28.8	73	18.7	36	9.3	36	9.3	389	100

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	Urban Sch.	78	21.5	83	22.9	38	10.4	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	Rural Sch.	64	16.5	100	25.7	67	17.2	99	25.4	59	15.2	389	100
	Urban Sch.	50	13.8	83	22.9	66	18.1	83	22.9	81	22.3	363	100
Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers Depression	Rural Sch.	170	43.7	122	31.4	39	9.9	36	9.3	22	5.7	389	100
	Urban Sch.	101	27.8	106	29.2	52	14.4	53	14.6	51	14.0	363	100
Experiencing communication problems	Rural Sch.	84	21.6	66	17.0	70	18.0	86	22.1	83	21.3	389	100
	Urban Sch.	68	18.7	74	20.4	58	16.0	94	25.9	69	19.0	363	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indiscipline	Rural Sch.	99	25.4	70	18.0	56	14.4	80	20.6	84	21.6	389	100
	Urban Sch.	69	19.0	90	24.8	58	16.0	76	20.9	70	19.3	363	100
Fear of losing friends	Rural Sch.	87	22.4	84	21.6	47	12.0	75	19.3	96	24.7	389	100
	Urban Sch.	68	18.8	88	24.3	53	14.4	84	23.2	70	19.3	363	100
Fear of being punished	Rural Sch.	78	20.1	84	21.6	51	13.1	77	19.8	99	25.4	389	100
	Urban Sch.	80	22.0	90	24.8	65	19.0	71	19.6	53	14.6	363	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	Rural Sch.	96	24.7	83	21.3	69	17.8	72	18.5	69	17.7	389	100
	Urban Sch.	84	23.1	90	24.8	65	17.9	71	19.6	53	14.6	363	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	Rural Sch.	94	24.2	85	21.9	42	10.7	66	17.0	102	26.2	389	100
	Urban Sch.	115	31.7	78	21.5	37	10.2	52	14.3	81	22.3	363	100

Table 9. Perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between male and female teachers.

Statement	Gender	Strongly agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Experiencing mental illness	Male	125	59.2	40	19.0	7	3.4	24	11.8	14	5.6	211	100
	Female	88	57.5	28	18.3	3	2.0	21	13.7	13	4.4	153	100
Being over confident	Male	12	5.7	49	23.2	13	6.2	24	11.4	12	5.7	211	100
	Female	16	10.5	37	24.2	6	3.9	20	13.1	16	10.5	153	100
Being a talkative	Male	11	5.2	21	10.0	118	55.9	46	21.8	8	3.8	16.6	100
	Female	7	4.6	23	15.0	6	6.2	99	64.7	12	7.8	153	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	Male	7	6	145	68.7	15	7.1	35	16.6	7	6	211	100
	Female	10	10.3	83	54.2	19	12.4	29	19.0	11	11.3	153	100
Ethnic violence	Male	34	16.1	153	72.5	7	3.3	15	7.1	2	9	211	100
	Female	34	22.2	95	62.1	5	3.3	17	11.1	2	1.3	153	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	Male	20	9.5	143	67.8	17	5.2	30	19.6	4	1.9	211	100
	Female	12	7.8	97	63.4	8	3.3	7	3.3	6	3.9	153	100
Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers Depression	Male	137	64.7	58	28.0	6	2.0	7	3.3	13	6.9	211	100
	Female	42	14.7	102	62.1	4	2.6	3	2.0	42	27.5	153	100
Experiencing communication problems	Male	111	52.6	59	28.0	19	5.9	23	10.9	1	5	211	100
	Female	20	13.1	95	62.1	9	9.2	27	17.6	2	1.3	153	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indiscipline	Male	106	50.2	41	19.4	18	8.5	40	19.0	6	2.8	211	100
	Female	9	5.9	102	66.7	12	7.8	24	15.7	6	2.9	153	100

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Fear of losing friends	Male	12	5.7	44	20.9	109	51.7	35	16.6	11	5.2	211	100
	Female	9	5.9	38	24.8	6	3.9	85	55.6	15	9.8	153	100
Fear of being punished	Male	12	10.3	43	37.1	16	13.8	35	30.2	10	8.6	211	100
	Female	9	9.3	38	39.2	6	6.1	34	35.1	10	10.3	153	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	Male	14	6.6	34	16.1	116	55.0	39	18.5	8	3.8	211	100
	Female	8	5.2	89	58.2	12	7.8	31	20.3	13	8.5	153	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	Male	11	5.2	33	15.6	9	4.3	139	65.9	19	9.0	211	100
	Female	7	4.6	85	55.6	9	5.9	35	22.9	17	11.1	153	100

In addition, 41.2% of the teachers in rural schools and 41.7% of the teachers in urban schools agreed that being fearful and lack of confidence contributes to violence among students. However, 2.3 and 45.2% of the teachers in rural and urban schools were in disagreement with the statement. Experiencing anxiety problems was supported by 92.7% of the teachers in rural schools and 83.6% of the teachers in urban schools. However, the statement was not supported by 2.3 and 3.4% of the teachers in rural and urban schools, respectively. In addition, experiencing communication problems was supported by 80.8% of the teachers in rural schools and 40.7% of the teachers in urban schools, while 11 and 17.5% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. The teachers in rural and urban schools who agreed with the statement that fear of being labelled a deviant or indiscipline in the teachers is a cause of violence, accounted for 71.2 and 75.2% of the teachers in rural and urban schools, respectively. However, disagreement with the statement was expressed by 20.4 and 21.1% of the teachers in rural and urban schools, respectively. Fear of losing friends was supported by 74.3% of the teachers in rural schools and 33.5% of the teachers in urban schools, while 20.4 and 59.1% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Respondents who expressed agreement with the statement of fear of being punished formed 41.7% of the teachers in rural schools and 46.8% of the teachers in urban schools. However, 45.2 and 34.2% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Desire to uphold high parental expectations was supported by 20.4% of the teachers in rural schools and 21.3% of the teachers in urban schools, while 21 and 20.7% of the teachers in rural and urban schools respectively, were in disagreement with the statement. Both teachers in rural and urban schools who

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were in agreement with the statement that desire to be loved by both parents and teachers contribute to violence among students formed 19.4 and 57.3%, respectively. However, 77% of the teachers in rural schools and 36.5% of the teachers in urban schools were in disagreement with the statement.

In order to test if there was any significant difference in perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between teachers in rural schools and teachers in urban schools, a t-test statistics was used. The t-test statistics under the assumption of unequal variances had a value of 0.147 and the degree of freedom had a value of -1.456 with an associated two tail significance level of 0.000. Since the significance value of 0.000 was less than $\alpha = 0.05$, it implied that teachers in rural schools differed significantly from teachers in urban schools in their perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour among secondary schools. Stafford and Cornell (2003) found that psychopathic scores predicted aggressive behavior among 72 adolescent psychiatric inpatients. This concurs with the findings of the current study which reported that mental illness was one of the psychological factors contributing to violence among students.

Table 10. Perceptions of psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour between teachers in rural secondary schools (Rural Sch.) and teachers in urban secondary schools (Urban Sch.).

Statement	Location of school	Strongly agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Experiencing mental illness	Rural Sch.	120	62.8	24	13.4	6	3.1	22	11.5	9	4.7	191	100
	Urban Sch.	93	53.8	34	17.4	4	2.3	24	13.9	18	10.4	173	100
Being over confident	Rural Sch.	131	46.6	23	23.6	7	4.5	23	35.9	16	4.6	191	100
	Urban Sch.	54	37.8	54	37.8	2	5.6	12	4.0	8	12.5	173	100
Being a talkative	Rural Sch.	8	4.2	19	9.9	113	59.2	39	20.4	12	6.3	191	100
	Urban Sch.	10	5.8	25	5.9	11	11	106	61.3	21	12.1	173	100
Fear of uncertainty of unemployment in future	Rural Sch.	8	4.2	134	70.0	15	7.9	27	14.1	7	3.7	191	100
	Urban Sch.	10	3.8	94	53.4	19	14.0	37	21.4	13	7.5	173	100
Ethnic violence	Rural Sch.	30	15.7	147	73.8	6	3.1	13	6.8	1	1.0	191	100
	Urban Sch.	38	22.0	107	68.8	6	3.5	19	10.1	3	1.7	173	100
Fear and lack of self confidence	Rural Sch.	64	16.5	50	24.7	67	17.2	99	25.4	59	15.2	191	100
	Urban Sch.	50	13.8	53	27.9	66	18.1	83	22.9	81	22.3	173	100

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Experiencing anxiety problems, for example, tempers Depression	Rural Sch.	131	68.6	46	24.1	5	2.6	7	1.3	2	1.0	191	100
	Urban Sch.	48	27.7	114	65.9	5	2.9	3	1.7	3	1.7	173	100
Experiencing communication problems	Rural Sch.	107	56.0	47	24.8	16	8.4	21	11.0	0	0	191	100
	Urban Sch.	48	13.9	107	16.8	10	5.8	29	16.8	3	0.7	173	100
Fear of being labeled a deviant or indisciplin	Rural Sch.	103	53.9	34	17.3	15	7.9	35	18.3	4	2.1	191	100
	Urban Sch.	12	6.9	109	68.3	15	8.7	25	16.5	8	4.6	173	100
Fear of losing friends	Rural Sch.	14	7.3	148	67.0	10	5.2	31	16.2	8	4.2	191	100
	Urban Sch.	13	7.5	25	26.0	14	8.1	92	53.9	9	5.2	173	100
Fear of being punished	Rural Sch.	78	20.1	84	21.6	51	13.1	77	19.8	99	25.4	191	100
	Urban Sch.	80	22.0	90	24.8	65	19.0	71	19.6	53	14.6	173	100
Desire to uphold high parental expectations	Rural Sch.	12	6.3	27	14.1	112	58.6	32	16.8	8	4.2	191	100
	Urban Sch.	10	5.8	96	15.5	16	9.2	38	13.2	13	7.5	173	100
Desired to be loved by both parents and teachers	Rural Sch.	7	3.7	30	15.7	7	3.7	131	68.6	16	8.4	191	100
	Urban Sch.	11	6.4	88	50.9	11	6.4	48	24.9	20	11.6	173	100

DISCUSSION

Forms of violence

Violent behavior is a contemporary crucial issue among secondary school students. There are various forms of violent behavior as perceived by students and teachers in public secondary schools. Male students perceive the forms of violence in order of seriousness as follows: sexual violence, rioting, bullying and fighting. On the other hand, female students identified the forms of violence as: bullying, fighting, rioting and sexual violence. Generally, there was no significant difference between male and female students in their perception of forms of violence among secondary school students. Male teachers perceived the following forms of violence in order of seriousness: bullying, rioting, fighting and sexual violence. On the other hand, female teachers identified the following as forms of violence in order of seriousness: rioting, fighting, sexual violence and bullying. However, there was no significant difference in the perceptions of forms of violence among teachers. The findings of the current study concurred with the one conducted by Kadzamira (2000) who observed that sexual harassment of girls

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by male teachers was common in rural schools in Malawi. The current study differed with that conducted by Nansel et al. (2001) who conducted a survey of 15,686 students in grades 6 - 10 in public and private schools within the United States. They reported that 29.9% of the sample had been involved in bullying, 13% of the students acknowledged that they were bullies, 10.6% reported being victims and 6.3% admitted being both a bully and a victim. However, Nansel and others did not establish other forms of violence experienced among students as perceived by teachers in urban and rural schools.

Psychological factors contributing to violent behavior

The main psychological factors contributing to violent behaviour were as follows: experiencing anxiety problems, ethnic violence, experiencing mental problem, fearful and lack of self confidence and fear of being punished. Others included being overconfident, experiencing communication problems, fear of being a deviant or undisciplined, fear of losing friends, fear of being punished, desire to uphold high parental expectations, desire to be loved by both parents and teachers and being talkative. Inability to meet parental expectations such as high academic performance may make a student to be violent. This shortcoming may be due to genetic makeup, low economic status and physical impairment. Such a student may displace his inability by bullying or fighting his colleagues. These findings concur with those of Stafford and Cornell (2003) who found that psychopathic scores predicted aggressive behavior among 72 adolescent psychiatric inpatients. This concurs with the findings of the current study which report that mental illness is one of the psychological factors that is contributing to violence among students. Similarly, Murrie et al. (2004) found out that there was a relationship between psychopath scores and violent behavior in incarcerated adolescents. The findings of the present study are also similar to those of Langerspetz et al. (1982) who established that victims of violence with low esteem were subjectively maladjusted and thus, experienced peer relations negatively.

In a study on the relationship between age and bullying behavior, Olweus (1993) compared data from primary and secondary schools. He found the incidents of bullying to be twice as high in primary schools as it is in secondary schools. This finding is dissimilar to the findings of the current study in which respondents identified psychological factors that contribute to violent behaviour in secondary schools. In addition, Perry et al. (1988) studied student rejection by peers. They found out that victimization was not significantly related to age, sex and the victims' level of aggression, but there was significant positive correlation between victimization and peer rejection. This is dissimilar to the findings of the current study that established other psychological factors contributing to violent behaviour in secondary schools as perceived by students.

Conclusion

In relation to the findings of the study, it is concluded that violent behavior is still a challenge in secondary schools. Respondents were able to identify forms and psychological factors contributing to violent behavior in secondary schools. The forms of violence included: sexual violence, bullying, fighting and rioting. The perceived physiological factors that were identified by respondents included:

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being physically strong, being older in school, having an average appearance, being the tallest in school and having physical disabilities. Since violence is probably the greatest source of distress among secondary school students today, a concerted effort from teachers and parents is highly needed to control or stamp it out of schools. As such, victims of violence ought to be counseled. If they are hurt, then they should be referred to medical doctors for treatment. Importantly, they should be referred to psychiatrists and school counselors, if any mental and psychological disorders were detected. In addition, guidance and counseling should be streamlined in schools in order to reduce cases of violent behavior.

REFERENCES

- Bandura A (1977). Social Learning Theory. Prentice-hall, Englewood cliff, N. J. Council: Washington, DC.
- Coie JD, Dodge KA, Coppote ill H (1982). Dimension and types of social status. Across age perspective. Dev. Psychol., 18: 557-70.
- Fisher A, Laing J, Stoeckel J (1983). A handbook for family planning operations research design. New York: The population Council.
- Kadzamira E (2000). Sexual harassment in schools. East African Standard, November 11, p. 13
- Kaiser B, Rasminsky JS (2003). Challenging behavior in young children: Understanding, preventing, and responding effectively. Boston: Pearson.
- Kigotho W (1999). "Why Students become bullies." The Standard on Saturday, November 19, p.13.
- Kisia A (2010). Rioting Students Burn Dormitory. Daily Nation, February 27, p. 8.
- Kuchio T, Njagi E (2008). Central Province School hit hard by strikes, Education. Nairobi: Shrend Publishers and suppliers Ltd. July 31. p. 11.
- Langerspetz KM, Bjorkquist K, Bertz M, King E (1982). Group Aggression among School Children in Three Schools.
- Leach F (2003). Learning to be violent: the role of the school in developing adolescent gendered behaviour. Compare, 33: 385-400.

Michigan Journal of Multidisciplinary Research

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Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/MJMR/issue/view/198>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Loper AB, Hoffschmidt SJ, Ash E (2001). Personality features and characteristics of violent events committed by juvenile offenders. *Behavioral Sci. Law*, 19: 81-96.

Mathiu M (2008). No party is innocent in school fires tragedy. *Daily Nation* of July 26.

Murrie D, Cornell D, Kaplan S, McConville S, Levy Elkon A (2004). Psychopathy scores and violence among juvenile offenders: A multimeasure study. *Behavioral Sci. Law*, 22: 49-67.

Nansel TR, Overpeck M, Pilla RS, Ruan WJ, Simons-Morton B, Scheidt P (2001). Bullying behaviors among U.S. youth: Prevalence and association with psychosocial adjustment. *J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 285: 1094-2100.

Ohsako T (2007). *Studies in comparative Education. Violence at school: Global issues and Interventions.* UNESCO. International Bureau of Education, 1997. Lausanne: Switzerland by Presses Centrales.

Olweus D (1999). *Bullying prevention program.* Boulder, CO: Center for the Study and Prevention of Violence, Institute of Behavioral Science, University of Colorado at Boulder.

Olweus S (1993). *Bullying at School. What we know and we can do.*

Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.

Perry DG, Kusel SJ, Perry LC (1988). Victims of peer aggressive. *Dev. Psychol.*, 24: 807-814.

Ruto JS (2009). *Sexual Abuse of School Age Children: Evidence from Kenya.* CICE Hiroshima University, *J. Int. Cooperation Educ.*, 12(1): 177-192.

Seals D, Young J (2003). Bullying and victimization: Prevalence and relationship to gender, grade level, ethnicity, self-esteem, and depression. *Adolescence*, 38: 735-747.

Stafford E, Cornell D (2003). Psychopathy scores predict adolescent inpatient aggression. *Assessment*, 10: 1-11.

Unnever J, Cornell DG (2003). Bullying, self control, and ADHD. *J. Interpersonal Violence*, 18: 129-147.